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Research Article

Assessment Inflammatory Marker And Its Relationship With Liver Enzymes In Patients With Chronic Liver Failure

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Keeping the body's metabolic rate in check is one of the liver's most important functions, and the organ's capacity to control its own size is fundamental to good health. However, liver damage from different causes can have serious effects on its function, leading to inflammation, damage to liver cells, and other complications. So this study aimed to assessment the inflammatory marker and its relationship with liver enzymes.

Materials and method:

Researchers at Al-Hussein Teaching Hospital in Thi-Qar Governorate evaluated chronic liver failure patients from August 20, 2023, until February 25, 2024. The study included 40 chronic liver failure patients and 40 controls aged 20–60.

Results:

The investigation found elevated levels of TNF- α , IL-1 β , CRP, ALT, AST, and total bilirubin. Additionally, TNF- α , IL-1 β , CRP, ALT, AST, and total bilirubin showed a favorable connection.

Conclusion:

We discovered that inflammatory levels were much higher in patients compared to controls as our trial came to a close. There was also discovered a favorable relationship between TNF- α and IL-1 β , CRP, ALT, AST and total bilirubin.

INTRODUCTION

The capacity of the liver to control its own size in respect to the body is fundamental for general well-being, since it is responsible for preserving metabolic equilibrium. However, liver injuries may cause inflammation, cell damage, and other issues that affect liver function (1). After tissue

damage and cell death, IL-1 family cytokines produce inflammatory and Th2-associated cytokines (2). Liver injuries release DAMPs or PAMPs that excite Kupffer cells and other immune cells. Activation causes the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such TNF- α and IL-1 β (3). Residents, or Kupffer cells, and monocyte-

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derived hepatocytic macrophages also cause liver disease. Tissue damage and liver homeostasis deteriorate in an inflammatory environment. Inflammation activates hepatic stellate cells (HSCs), which deposit excess ECM proteins like collagen, damaging liver tissue and causing fibrosis (4). In response to liver injury, myofibroblasts become repairing and fibrosis-inducing cells (5). Several inflammatory indicators and cytokines may predict early mortality and cause rapid decompensation, according to (6,7) It is uncertain whether these variables may predict liver failure-related hospitalizations and deaths (8). The present study examined chronic liver failure patients' inflammatory markers. This assessment used routine clinical liver examinations, which included Alanine aminotransferase is abundant in hepatocyte cytoplasm. In general, healthy persons have lower serum ALT. Serum levels of aspartate amino transferase (AST), which transforms aspartate and α -ketoglutarate into oxaloacetate and glutamate, considerably increase after hepatocyte apoptosis and injury (9,10). Bilirubin, a tetrapyrrolic molecule produced by heme catabolism, is found in all cells but is abundant in the liver, heart, and skeletal muscles (11,12,13). (Vítek & Tiribelli, 2021). An inflammatory indicator that includes among the cytokines involved in disease development, including liver damage, is tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α). It regulates metabolism, cell proliferation, immune system development, and cell survival (14) found that IL-1 β , a cytokine that promotes inflammation, has a significant role in chronic liver failure development, especially in cases with inflammation and fibrosis. The causes of chronic liver failure depend on this cytokine. Barbier et al.'s 2019 research and CRP, an acute-phase protein known to suggest inflammation. Inflammation causes liver output to rise, making it a reliable clinical predictor of disease activity (15).

High C-reactive protein levels have a limited connection with inflammatory disease prognoses (16). Research aimed to measure blood liver enzymes, TNF- α , IL-1 β , and CRP levels. To determine the correlation between liver enzyme levels and TNF- α and IL-1 β .

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A group of individuals suffering from long term liver issues participated in the study conducted at Al Hussein Teaching Hospital, in Thi Qar Governorate. The research took place between August 20 2023 and February 25 2024. Between the ages of 20 and 60, the research included 80 participants, 40 of whom had chronic liver failure and 40 of whom served as controls. Before being separated in a centrifuge at 3000 xg, around five milliliters of blood were taken and left to clot at room temperature for ten minutes in disposable tubes. In order to preserve the serum samples for further biochemical parameter measurement, they were separated and kept at a temperature of -20 degrees Celsius until needed. The reagents were given by (Linear, Spain) and the serum was used for AST and ALT measurement. (Biolabo, France) provided the reagents used to test tuberculosis (TB). Elabscience Biotech. Inc., USA, produced the ready kits used to assess IL-1 β , TNF- α , and CRP by the Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA).

Statistical Analysis

We analyzed data with SPSS 23.0. We reported the results as mean $\pm$ SD. Analyzed parameter differences among groups using a t-test with a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$. We searched for variable associations using Pearson's correlation.

RESULTS

Table 1 displays the total bilirubin and liver enzyme values in both the patients and the controls. When comparing the patient group to the control group, researchers discovered that the levels of serum bilirubin, AST, and ALT was much higher in the former.

Table 1- Levels of liver enzymes and Total bilirubin in controls and patients

Patients	Control	Parameters	p.value
68.34± 9.24	29.87±4.19	ALT (IU/L)	0.001
54.85± 11.43	18.24 ± 5.41	AST (IU/L)	0.000
7.38 ± 1.24	0.51 ± 0.09	Total bilirubin (mg/dl)	0.000

Table 2 displays IL-1 β , TNF- α , and CRP levels in controls and patients. Serum IL-1 β , TNF- α , and CRP concentrations were significantly higher in the patient group compared to the control group.

Table 2- Levels of liver IL-1 β , TNF- α and CRP in controls and patients

Parameters	Controls	Patients	p-value
IL-1 β (pg/mL)	0.87±0.14	3.56 ± 1.09	0.000
TNF- α (pg/mL)	2.45± 0.73	7.49±1.24	0.006
CRP (mg/L)	1.54 ±0.65	8.38 ± 2.37	0.017

Table 3 show the is a positive correlation between IL-1 β and CRP. Also it was found a a positive correlation between ALT, AST and total bilirubin.

TNF- α with	r	p-value	Result
IL-1 β	0.51	0.022	Positively significant correlation
CRP	0.73	0.001	Positively significant correlation
ALT	0.44	0.040	Positively significant correlation
AST	0.48	0.000	Positively significant correlation

DISSECTION

A healthy liver balances "resistance" and "tolerance" as a frontline immune organ. With its dual blood supply of hepatic artery arterial blood and portal-venous blood conveying intestinal products, it acts as a gatekeeper. On one hand, the liver monitors immunity. The liver has numerous resident antigen presentation cells strategically placed for "border control." (17) The reticuloendothelial system, which includes dendritic cells and endothelial cells (Kupffer cells), is involved in these activities. Upon pathogen detection, these cells set in motion coordinated immune responses that flush out the invaders, bring in white blood cells, and introduce lymphocytes to antigens inside the unique hepatic vasculature. Proinflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-6 (IL-6) and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-alpha) activate the liver to produce a number of proteins that are important to both the innate and adaptive immune responses. The liver also plays an important role in local monitoring. Appropriate proteins during the acute phase

include complement factors and C-reactive and lipopolysaccharide binding proteins. (18). Liver failure increases hepatocyte mortality due to the cascade of events that starts with inflammatory mediator production, immune cell activation, and inflammatory cytokines. Studies have linked TNF- α and IL-1 β to poor liver failure prognosis [19,20,21]. Serum factors may alter MSCs' immunomodulatory activity and liver disease therapy effectiveness (22,23,24). Serum TNF IL-1 and CRP increased significantly in this liver enzyme and inflammatory marker study. This associated favorably with liver enzymes. Recent studies highlight the significance of TNF- α and IL-1 β in liver failure and their potential as therapeutic targets. Patients with liver failure have higher TNF- α and IL-1 β levels owing to hepatic inflammation and immune response dysregulation. Liver damage from chronic liver failure leads to inflammation and secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines including TNF- α and IL-1 β . These cytokines increase inflammation, immune cell

recruitment, hepatic stellate cell activation, and liver fibrosis/cirrhosis (25-28).

CONCLUSION

At the conclusion of the study we conducted, it was found that levels of inflammation had increased significantly in patients compared to controls. Also it was found a positive correlation between TNF- α and "IL-1 β , CRP, ALT, AST and total bilirubin".

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